

doi:10.5281/zenodo.15320739

Pricing Orientation, Pricing Capability And Effectiveness Of Private Secondary Schools In Northwest, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the relationship between pricing orientation, pricing capability, and the effectiveness of private secondary schools in Northwestern Nigeria. Despite the critical role private schools play in expanding educational access and delivering quality learning experiences, affordability remains a major constraint, especially in economically disadvantaged regions. Drawing on the Market Orientation Theory and Dynamic Capabilities Theory, the study explores whether pricing orientation and capability influence private school effectiveness measured by student enrolment and retention. A descriptive correlational research design was adopted, and data were gathered from 206 private school managers across five states using a validated questionnaire. Findings reveal that both pricing orientation, particularly value and competition-oriented pricing and pricing capability, especially price information and negotiation capabilities, positively and significantly correlate with school effectiveness. The study concludes by highlighting the importance of deliberate, data-driven pricing strategies in enhancing educational outcomes and sustaining private school operations. It recommends among others, context-sensitive pricing policies to improve access and performance in the private education sector.

Keywords: Pricing Orientation, capability, Effectiveness, Private schools

INTRODUCTION

The significance of private secondary schools extends beyond their provision of quality education that meets parental expectations and contributes to socio-economic development. Their presence also ensures that parents have diverse educational options to choose from (Ogunkola & Adekola, 2017; Ibrahim, 2018). Notably, these institutions have played a critical role in expanding educational access, particularly in regions where public school infrastructure is inadequate. Moreover, they serve families desiring alternative or superior educational standards compared to those offered by nearby public schools. Given these advantages, the effectiveness of private schools becomes essential.

The effectiveness of private schools can be gauged by the quality of education they offer, often reflected in their ability to attract and retain students (Atolabge et al., 2019). However, in Northwestern Nigeria, many families find access to private schooling constrained by high costs, making it unaffordable for those with limited income (USAID, 2021; Ibrahim, 2018). This financial barrier is particularly pressing in the Northwestern region, where living expenses continue to rise amidst difficult economic conditions. The

tuition and other costs linked to private education are often prohibitively high, especially for low-income households (USAID, 2021; Wycliffe, 2019; Ibrahim, 2018). Consequently, a large portion of the population remains unable to benefit from private education (Blessing et al., 2018).

Although private schools in Northwestern Nigeria have shown commendable academic outcomes (Ibrahim, 2018; Salahu, 2019), their affordability remains a significant challenge, as evidenced by low enrollment rates and frequent student withdrawals. Therefore, enhancing the effectiveness of these schools necessitates a strategic approach that tackles these issues while leveraging their existing contributions to the educational and economic landscape (Salahu, 2019). Addressing this issue involves setting school fees appropriately and justifiably (Agbaeze et al., 2020). This brings forth the need to explore whether school inefficiencies stem from poor pricing strategies and inadequate pricing competencies. Empirical studies have demonstrated that effective pricing orientation can improve organizational performance in commercial industries (Agbaeze et al., 2020; Kankam-Kwarteng et al., 2019; Liozu & Hinteruber, 2013) and within higher education institutions (Junaris, 2022; Amir et al., 2016; Mailah et al., 2012). Likewise, scholars argue that pricing capabilities can enhance firm performance in the business sector (Upiri et al., 2021; Skarmeas et al., 2014). However, little to no research has explored these factors in the context of private secondary education in Northwestern Nigeria. To address this gap, the present study aims to investigate the relationship between school effectiveness, pricing orientation, and pricing capability within this under-researched educational setting.

Research Objectives

- i. To study the level of effectiveness, pricing orientation and pricing capability in private secondary schools in Northwestern Nigeria.
- ii. To establish the relationship between pricing orientation and private school effectiveness in Northwestern Nigeria
- iii. To establish the relationship between pricing capability and private school effectiveness in Northwestern Nigeria

Research Questions

- i. What is the level of effectiveness, pricing orientation and pricing capability in private secondary schools in Northwestern Nigeria?
- ii. Is there a significant relationship between pricing orientation and private school effectiveness in Northwestern Nigeria?
- iii. Is there a significant relationship between pricing capability and private school effectiveness in Northwestern Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

- i. There no significant relationship between pricing orientation and private school effectiveness in Northwestern Nigeria
- ii. There no significant relationship between pricing capability and private school effectiveness in Northwestern Nigeria

LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical Review

This study reviewed Market Orientation Theory and Dynamic Capabilities Theory as theoretical guide for the study. Market orientation theory for pricing orientation was proposed by Kohli and Jaworski (1990). They posit that market-oriented firms understand customer needs, market trends, and competitor actions. For private schools, adopting a value-based pricing orientation (pricing based on perceived value to the customer) in addition to cost-plus or competitor-based pricing can increase both enrollment and customer satisfaction. Pricing capability, which is defined as an institution's ability to design, execute, and manage pricing strategies, is a dynamic capability. Teece et al. (1997) proposed dynamic capability theory, arguing that organizations must develop such capabilities to respond to market changes. For private

schools, especially those facing affordability constraints, developing pricing capabilities becomes essential to sustaining operations and enhancing effectiveness.

Conceptual Review

Private School Effectiveness

Private school effectiveness has been described as how well a school is able to achieve its goals, deliver quality education, and produce positive outcomes for students (Cohen-Vogel et al., 2015; Darling-Hammond, 2010). Private school effectiveness refers to the degree to which a private school is successful in achieving financial viability (Day-Ashley et al., 2014). It is also viewed the degree to which a private school is successful in achieving financial objectives of its stakeholders (Sammons et al., 2015). There are various metrics of measuring private school effectiveness, depending on the point of interest to the researcher. Private school effectiveness can be measured in terms of new students' enrollment, students' retention, school expansion and profitability, in line with the argument by many scholars that effectiveness of profit organization can be measure through such indicators as acquisition of new customers, retention of old customers, business expansion and profitability (Kankam-Kwarteng et al., 2019; Wawaka & Muchelule, 2018; Liozu & Hinterhuber, 2013). However, the present study considered students enrolment and retention as measures of private school effectiveness.

Pricing Orientation

Pricing orientation has been defined by Liozu et al. (2012) from a firm's strategic perspective as all pricing practices, methods, behaviors and processes leading to pricing decisions with the goal of maintaining and sustaining firm competitive advantage. Pricing orientation has also been defined as the explicit steps and procedures through which pricing decisions are established (Amir et al., 2016). In the present study, pricing orientation refers to the underlying processes and strategies that guide education institutions on how to make school fees decision.

Scholars argued that effectiveness of profit organisations is tied to their pricing orientation in determining prices in various industries including manufacturing companies, financial institutions, retail companies across the globe (Liozu & Hinterhuber; 2013), export industries in Europe (Skarmas et al., 2014), public tertiary institutions in Malaysia (Amir et al., 2016), private universities in Nigeria (Olaoye et al., 2018; Murtala et al., 2019), automobile service industries in Ghana (Kankam-Kwargeng et al., 2019) and Supermarkets in Nieria (Agbaeze et al., 2020). According to Amir et al. (2016), a comprehensive review of scholarly literature of pricing in both manufacturing and service sectors have identified various pricing approaches, which, generally, fall into three main dimensions; value-oriented, competition-oriented and cost-oriented pricing. Therefore, pricing orientation was measured in this study based on value-oriented, competition-oriented and cost-oriented pricing.

Pricing Capability

Pricing capability is a crucial factor in setting the appropriate prices for private school services. This is because, it has been found in the literature to strongly influence the financial performance of business organizations (Choi & Kim, 2017; Skameas et al., 2014; Liozu & Hinterhuber, 2013; Afzal, 2009). Pricing Capability is the ability of an organisation to set and mange price for optimal revenue (Skarmas, et al., 2014). In the context of private education, pricing capability can be defined as the ability of private schools to set and mange school fees.

Scholars argued that the constructs for measuring pricing capability should be developed based on the situation of the organization being studied (Upiri et al., 2021; Afzal, 2009). Based on this argument, pricing capability was measured in terms of such dimensions as price bundling capability (Upiri et al., 2021), price adaptive capability, price information capability, price negotiation capability and price formation capability (Liozu & Hinterhuber, 2013; Skarmas et al., 2014). These therefore, constitute the dimensions of measuring pricing capability. However, in line with the argument that the situation of the organization being studied should determine the constructs (Upiri et al., 2021; Afzal, 2009), the present study measured pricing capability based on price adaptive capability, information capability and

negotiation capability in consideration of the uniqueness of private school operation and socio-cultural and economic realities of Northwestern Nigeria.

Conceptual Model

Independent Variable I

Figure 1: Conceptual model of the study

Figure 1 represents a conceptual model showing the relationship between the two independent variables, pricing orientation and pricing capability and the dependent variable, private school effectiveness in Northwest, Nigeria. The model proposes two hypotheses. The first hypothesis is depicted by the path linking pricing orientation with private school effectiveness, showing possible association between pricing orientation and private school effectiveness, and the second hypothesis is shown by the path connecting pricing capability to private school effectiveness.

These proposed hypotheses show that the dependent variable (private school effectiveness) is influenced by each of pricing orientation and pricing capability, all which are independent variables (Liozu & Hinterhuber, 2013). The model also shows that private school effectiveness (dependent variable) is measured by such indicators as enrolment and retention (Liozu & Hinterhuber, 2013). Similarly, the model shows that pricing orientation is measured through value oriented pricing, competition oriented pricing and cost oriented pricing while pricing capability is measured based on adaptive, information and negotiation capabilities of pricing. Therefore, this model reflects a cause and effect relationships, suggesting that strengthening pricing orientation and pricing capability will lead to improved private school effectiveness.

Empirical Review

Various studies empirically established association existing among pricing orientation, pricing capability and organisational effectiveness. For example, empirical studies established an association between pricing orientation and organizational effectiveness in different industries. For instance, Agbaeze et al. (2020) examined how pricing orientation relates with organisational performance in supermarket settings in Enugu state of Nigeria. It was a quantitative study, employing correlational design, with data collected

through questionnaire administration, and analyzed using inferential statistics. The findings revealed that the three dimensions of pricing orientation are collectively associated with organizational performance. A similar study was carried out by Wawaka and Muchelule (2018) in cement industry in Kenya. The findings showed that pricing orientation positively relates with organisational performance. Furthermore, Kankam-Kwarteng et al. (2019) examined the influence of pricing orientation on organizational performance in automobile service sector in Ghana. The study found that pricing orientation influences the performance automobile service organisations.

Likewise, Liozu & Hinteruber (2013) conducted a global study to examine the influence of pricing orientation on firm performance, covering such industries as manufacturing firms, retail companies and services institutions. Using quantitative approach, the study found that the three dimensions of pricing orientation: value-oriented; completion-oriented; and cost-oriented pricing jointly influence organizational performance positively. However, assessment of the individual effect of these dimensions discovered that only value-oriented pricing significantly influences firm performance. Moreover, pricing orientation was found to be positively related to private universities in Southwestern Nigeria (Olaoye et al., 2018; Murtal et al., 2019), and to public higher institutions of learning in Malaysia ((Amir et al., 2016).

In addition to pricing orientation, pricing capability was empirically found to be positively associated with organizational effectiveness in various settings. For example, Skarmeas et al. (2014) examined the influence of pricing capability on firm performance in export industries. It was found that pricing capability significantly influences performance of export companies. Also, in global study that covers retail companies, service sector and manufacturing firms by Liozu & Hinteruber, (2013), it was empirically found that pricing capability influences firm performance. Similarly, Upiri et al. (2021) examined the effect of pricing capability on organizational performance in food and restaurant sector. It was found empirically that pricing capability has positive effect on organizational performance.

While empirical evidences confirmed the existence of positive relationships and effects of both pricing orientation and pricing capability on organizational performance in commercial and corporate sector, a thorough search for literature did not reveal any prior studies linking pricing orientation, pricing capability organisational effectiveness in the context of private secondary schools in North-western Nigeria, hence a need to fill this void.

RESEARCH METHODS

A quantitative approach was employed for this study, using a descriptive correlational design. The target population consists of 2565 proprietors/managers of private schools from five states purposely selected out of the seven states of Northwest, Nigeria. These states were selected on account of security issues that are more tensed in the two exempted states. A sample size of 346 was drawn using Slovin's formula [$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e^2)}$], to whom the questionnaire was administered. However, only 206 copies were retrieved and used for the analyses. Proportionate and simple random sampling methods were employed to select the respondents.

The research instrument used was a questionnaire, made up of four sections. Section A gathered personal information from the respondents, Section B focused on items related to pricing orientation (independent variable I), Section C addressed the constructs of pricing capability (independent variable II), and Section D contained items measuring private school effectiveness (dependent variable). The questionnaire was reviewed by a panel of experts, selected based on their experience and expertise in academia, as well as their proficiency in measurement and evaluation, for validation purposes. Based on the feedback from the panel, modifications were made to the original instrument. The content validity index (CVI) was computed and yielded a value of 0.75, indicating the instrument's validity. The reliability of the questionnaire was determined by calculating Cronbach's alpha using SPSS and pilot study data. All constructs achieved reliability scores above the benchmark of 0.7 (Amin, 2005).

Data was collected from 319 respondents by distributing the questionnaires and requesting their responses. The data collected was analyzed using statistical means to analyze the data related to objective one. For objectives two and three, Pearson’s product moment correlation (PPMC) coefficient was used to examine the relationships among pricing orientation, pricing capability and private school effectiveness. Finally, regression analysis was employed to analyze the data for objective four.

RESULTS

Data was analyzed based on the research the proposed research question/hypotheses

Research Question: What is the level of effectiveness, pricing orientation and pricing capability in private secondary schools in Northwestern Nigeria?

Level of Pricing Orientation

Table 1: Mean on Pricing Orientation

Organisational Justice	Mean	Interpretation
Value-oriented Pricing	3.62	High
Competition-oriented Pricing	3.53	High
Cost-oriented Pricing	2.99	Moderate
Grand Mean =	3.38	Moderate

Source: Field Data (2025)

Table 1 displays the mean scores showing the degree of agreement among managers of private schools on pricing orientation across the three constructs: value oriented, competition oriented, , and cost oriented pricing. The mean scores for these constructs range from 2.99 to 3.62. value oriented had the highest level of agreement with a mean score of 3.62, while cost oriented had the lowest, with a mean score of 2.99. The overall grand mean score for the three dimensions of pricing orientation was 3.38, which, based on the scale used, reflects a moderate level of agreement. This suggests that the perceived pricing orientation in private secondary schools in Northwest, Nigeria is moderate.

Level of Pricing Capability

Table 2: Mean on Pricing Capability

Attitude to Work	Mean	Interpretation
Price Adaptive capability	3.35	Moderate
Price Information Capability	3.82	High
Price Negotiation Capability	3.73	High
Overall Mean	3.63	High

Source: Field Data (2025)

The independent variable, pricing orientation, was categorized into three constructs: price adaptive capability, price information capability, , and price negotiation capability. The items used to measure these constructs were rated on a five-point Likert scale, with 1 representing "strongly disagree" (the lowest level of agreement) and 5 representing "strongly agree" (the highest level).

According to Table 2, price adaptive capability received a mean score of 3.35, which corresponds to "neutral" on the scale, reflecting a moderate evaluation of price adaptive capability. Price information capability earned a mean score of 3.82, indicating a positive assessment of the private school’s price information capability. Price negotiation capability also scored a mean of 3.73, aligning with "agree," which suggests a favorable evaluation of negotiation capability of private schools in terms of pricing their services. The overall mean score for pricing capability was 3.63, which corresponds to "agree" on the scale, indicating a generally good evaluation of pricing capability. This suggests that private schools in Northwestern Nigeria demonstrate a high level of pricing capability.

Level of Private school Effectiveness

Table 3: Mean on Private School Effectiveness

Organisational Justice	Mean	Interpretation
Enrolment	4.13	High
Retention	3.45	High
Overall Mean	3.79	High

Source: Field Data (2025)

Table 3 presents the two dimensions that define private school effectiveness as the dependent variables in the study: enrolment and retention. The table shows the mean scores representing the level of agreement among respondents regarding these aspects of private school effectiveness. The mean scores for these dimensions range from 3.45 to 4.13. Enrolment had the highest level of agreement, with a mean score of 4.1, while retention had the least (mean = 3.45). The overall mean score for the private school effectiveness was 3.79, which, on the scale used, corresponds to "agree," indicating a favorable overall rating by the respondents. This suggests that private secondary schools in Northwestern Nigeria demonstrate a high level effectiveness in terms of enrolment and retention.

Hypotheses:

Ho1: there is no significant relationship between pricing orientation and effectiveness of private secondary schools in Northwest, Nigeria

Table 4: Correlation between the Three Components of Pricing Orientation and Private School Effectiveness.

Variables	Pearson's r	P-value	decision	interpretation
Private School Effectiveness				
Value Oriented Pricing	0.502	P<0.01	Rejected	Significant
Competition Oriented Pricing	0.604	P<0.01	Rejected	Significant
Cost Oriented Pricing	0.434	P<0.01	Rejected	Significant

Source: Field Data (2025)

Table 4 displays the correlation results between the three dimensions of pricing orientation and private school effectiveness. As shown in the table, private school effectiveness was positively and significantly correlated with value oriented pricing ($r = 0.502$, $p < 0.01$). It also showed a strong positive association with competition oriented pricing ($r = 0.604$, $p < 0.01$). However, private school effectiveness was not significantly associated with cost oriented pricing ($r = 0.231$, $p > 0.01$).

Ho2: there is no significant relationship between pricing capability and effectiveness of private secondary schools in Northwest, Nigeria

Table 5: Correlation between the three components of pricing capability and private school effectiveness

Variables	Pearson's r	P-value	decision	interpretation
Private School Effectiveness				
Price adaptive capability	0.631	P<0.001	Not rejected	Insignificant
Price information capability	0.671	P<0.001	Rejected	Significant
Price negotiation capability	0.546	P<0.001	Rejected	Significant

Source: Field Data (2025)

To examine the relationship between each of the three constructs of pricing capability and the private school effectiveness, Pearson's linear correlation coefficient was applied at a 0.01 significance level with a two-tailed test. Table 5 presents the correlation results. As shown in the table, a significant positive relationship was found between price adaptive capability and private school effectiveness, with an r-value of 0.631 ($p < 0.01$). Price information capability also showed a significant positive relationship with private school effectiveness, with an r-value of 0.671 ($p < 0.01$). Similarly, price negotiation capability

demonstrated a significant positive correlation with private school effectiveness, with a Pearson's r-value of 0.546 ($p < 0.01$).

DISCUSSION

The findings on the level of pricing orientation showed that value oriented and competition oriented pricing received high levels of respondents' agreement while cost oriented pricing received moderate level of agreement. This suggests a reasonable level of orientation on school fees decision among private secondary schools. For value oriented pricing, the high level of agreement may be due to value creation in the school services, which were perceived beneficial by the parents, and aligning the school fees with the perceived value. Similarly, the high level of agreement for competition oriented pricing could reflect private schools' consideration of their competitors to set competitive school fees. The moderate level of cost oriented pricing might be attributed to the degree to which the cost of operation rises while financial capabilities of parents who patronize the services declined.

The findings on the level of pricing capability revealed that price information capability received the highest level of agreement. This could be attributed to several factors; private school' ability to use feedback from stakeholders, especially parents who are price sensitive, their ability to monitor their competitors' tactics, their ability to evaluate the fairness of their fees, and integrate all these to review their school fees. Price negotiation capability followed as the second-highest level of agreement, likely because private schools consider economic fluctuations in the country and how it affect financial stability of parents, based on which they offer opportunities for parents negotiate and agree on flexible payment modes and/or possible discount. Price adaptive capability obtained a moderate level of agreement, which might stem from difficulties in responding to market condition through balancing affordability with rising cost of operation.

The findings on private school effectiveness revealed high levels of agreement on both enrolment and retention. This indicates that private schools are able to employ quality teachers, acquire standard operational facilities and deliver services that are satisfactorily enough to attract potential students and retain the existing ones.

The findings on the relationship between the three dimensions of pricing orientation: value oriented pricing; competition oriented pricing; and cost oriented pricing, and private school effectiveness show a significant and positive correlation across all aspects, except for cost oriented pricing that shows insignificant correlation. Overall, the study reveals a significant positive relationship between pricing orientation and private school effectiveness. This implies that private schools that have and use underlying strategies and processes in setting school fees will be able to make a wise and justifiable fee decision, which will ultimately lead to the enhancement of their effectiveness. This finding aligns with previous researches indicating positive association between pricing orientation and organisational effectiveness (Agbaeze et al., 2020; Kankam-kwarteng et al., 2019; Olaoye et al., 2018; Amir et al., 2016).

The findings on the relationship between pricing capability and private school effectiveness revealed a positive correlation. All the three constructs of pricing capability; price adaptive capability, price information capability, and price negotiation capability, were found to have a significant and positive relationship with private school effectiveness. This finding is a reflection of private schools' ability to set and manage school fees amidst economic instability by adjusting their fees to reflect the conditions at hand, accessing and using relevant information in reviewing their fees, and negotiating with parents facing financial challenges to ease their payment methods. The implication of this is that private schools that are capable of managing their school fees through adapting to the changing conditions, negotiating with relevant stakeholders and collecting and using relevant data, will be able to achieve effectiveness through improved enrolment and retention. This finding agrees with that of Murtala et al. (2019), Skarmas et al. (2014) and Liou & Hinterhuber (2013), that pricing capability positively influences organizational performance.

CONCLUSION

This study examined the impact of pricing orientation and pricing capability on the effectiveness of private secondary schools in Northwestern Nigeria. Effectiveness was measured through two critical indicators: student enrolment and retention. The findings demonstrated that schools with strong value-oriented and competition-oriented pricing strategies were more likely to achieve higher effectiveness levels. Cost-oriented pricing, however, showed weaker association, indicating that pricing strategies solely based on operational costs may not resonate well with the socio-economic conditions of parents in the region.

Similarly, pricing capabilities, specifically in the areas of price information and negotiation—emerged as significant predictors of school effectiveness. These capabilities enabled schools to make informed, flexible, and context-sensitive decisions that align with stakeholder expectations and prevailing economic realities. Schools that effectively adapted their pricing, responded to market information, and engaged in fee negotiation showed better performance in attracting and retaining students.

In conclusion, pricing orientation and pricing capability are crucial internal strategic factors that influence the operational success of private schools in economically sensitive regions. Schools that adopt a deliberate, value-driven pricing framework and develop the capability to manage their pricing processes effectively are more likely to sustain enrolment and improve educational outcomes. Therefore, stakeholders in the education sector, particularly school managers and policy makers—should prioritize the development of pricing strategies and competencies as part of broader efforts to enhance school effectiveness and educational access in the region.

RECOMMENDATION

- i. Private school managers should prioritize value-oriented pricing approaches that align tuition fees with the perceived quality and benefits of education offered.
- ii. Training programs should be organized for school proprietors and administrators to develop core pricing competencies, especially in price information analysis, negotiation tactics, and adaptability.
- iii. In light of economic challenges faced by many households in Northwestern Nigeria, private schools should consider offering flexible payment plans and negotiating terms with financially constrained parents.
- iv. Schools should systematically gather and analyze data on competitors' pricing models, stakeholder expectations, and economic trends.
- v. Government agencies and educational regulators should support private schools by creating policies or subsidies that enable them to offer affordable tuition without compromising service quality.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The researchers wish to express their profound gratitude to the Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund) for the invaluable support and sponsorship of this research. The financial assistance provided by TETFund was instrumental in facilitating the successful execution of this study, enabling the collection of data, analysis, and completion of this project. This research would not have been possible without TETFund's commitment to fostering academic development and research excellence in tertiary institutions across Nigeria. We deeply appreciate the confidence placed in us and the recognition of the importance of investigating organizational justice, attitudes to work, and academic staff productivity in Kebbi State's tertiary institutions. Your unwavering dedication to advancing education and research in Nigeria is truly commendable. Thank you for contributing to the success of this study and for your enduring impact on the academic community.

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